

Statistical problems in the vitamin C trial with PCI patients by Shafaei-Bajestani et al. (2019)

Harri Hemilä¹

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There was no response by the authors by 2026-4-29.

Comment on:

Shafaei-Bajestani N, Talasaz AH, Salarifar M, Pourhosseini H, Sadri F, Jalali A.

Potential Role of Vitamin C Intracoronary Administration in Preventing Cardiac Injury After Primary Percutaneous Coronary Intervention in Patients with ST-Elevation Myocardial Infarction.

J Res Pharm Pract. 2019;8(2):75-82.

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31367642>

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<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC6636420>

Shafaei-Bajestani et al. write that “patients were randomly assigned to receive either the routine treatment plus Vitamin C (n = 126) or only the routine treatment (n = 126)” [1, p 77].

Thereafter, in the third paragraph of the results section, they write: “An increase by fivefold, the ULN [upper limit of normal] in the level of troponin T was significantly less frequent in the Vitamin C group (91.5% vs. 93.8%; P = 0.009), as was the rise by threefold, the ULN in the level of troponin T (94.4% vs. 97.2%; P = 0.078)” [1, p 77].

For the fivefold increase of troponin over the ULN level, the proportion 91.5% corresponds to 115 participants out of 126, and the proportion 93.8% corresponds to 118 participants out of 126. Comparison of 115/126 vs. 118/126 gives P(chi-2 test) = 0.47 [2,3]. This is very far from the reported P = 0.009.

Similarly, for the threefold increase of troponin over the ULN level, the proportion 94.4% corresponds to 119 participants out of 126, and the proportion 97.2% corresponds to 122 participants out of 126. Comparison of 119/126 vs. 122/126 gives P(chi-2 test) = 0.35 [2,3]. This is far from the reported P = 0.078.

In the same paragraph, Shafaei-Bajestani et al. write further that “the levels of CKMB more than fivefold and threefold the ULN were also significantly reduced by Vitamin C treatment compared with the control group (60.8% vs. 69.9%; P = 0.031 and 72% vs. 78.2%; P = 0.088, respectively)” [1, p 77].

1 Harri Hemilä, MD, PhD

Department of Public Health, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, FINLAND.

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

For the fivefold increase of CKMB over the ULN level, the proportion 60.8% corresponds to 77 participants out of 126, and the proportion 69.9% corresponds to 88 participants out of 126. Comparison of 77/126 vs. 88/126 gives $P(\text{chi-2 test}) = 0.15$ [2,3]. This is far from the reported $P = 0.031$.

Similarly, for the threefold increase of CKMB over the ULN level, the proportion 72% corresponds to 91 participants out of 126, and the proportion 78.2% corresponds to 99 participants out of 126. Comparison of 91/126 vs. 99/126 gives $P(\text{chi-2 test}) = 0.24$ [2,3]. This is far from the reported $P = 0.088$.

Thus, all of the four P-values reported in the paragraph about threefold and fivefold increases above ULN are incorrect.

Shafaei-Bajestani et al. write about the comparison of the mean levels of troponin between the trial arms: "In the study of primary end-point, serum levels of troponin T after 12 h were significantly lower in the study group than in the control group ($P = 0.003$) [Figure 2]" [1, p 77].

With a graphics program, from the Shafaei-Bajestani Figure 2 [1], I measured that the troponin level in the vitamin C group was 7.06 and in the control group 7.54 (reported on the logarithmic scale). However, there is no information of the SD or SE on which the $P = 0.003$ is based.

Shafaei-Bajestani et al. also write about the comparison of the mean levels of CKMB between the trial arms: "The serum level of CKMB after 6 h ($P = 0.00$) [Figure 2] ... significantly reduced by Vitamin C treatment" [1, p 77]. However, again there is no information of the SD or SE on which the $P = 0.00$ is based. In addition, there is no information to which actual P-value the expression 0.00 refers to.

Given the errors in the P-values described above, and because the data required for an appropriate analysis are not presented, the statistical significance of the differences in the troponin and CKMB levels between the trial arms cannot be considered to have been established.

Furthermore, Shafaei-Bajestani et al. the trial report states: "The present study ... in Tehran Heart Center affiliated with Tehran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran (Registration No. IRCT201606048698N19 at <http://www.irct.ir>)" [1, p 76]. However, that trial registration record does not mention Shafaei-Bajestani, troponin or CKMB [4]. Instead, that record states "the flow grade (Thrombolysis In Myocardial Infarction (TIMI) and (MPG) Myocardial Perfusion Grade" [4], which are not reported by Shafaei-Bajestani et al. [1].

Search of the Iranian Registry of Clinical Trials (IRCT) <http://www.irct.ir> with the name Shafaei-Bajestani finds 3 records, one of which is IRCT201706168698N21 [5]. That record appears consistent with the trial report by Shafaei-Bajestani et al. [1]. That registration states: "Blood samples will be collected in the study patients before and 6 and 18 hours after PCI to measure CKMB and Troponin I and two groups will compared" [5]. That record also states: "On the blood samples taken from these two groups for zero-hour clock and 6 clocks NGAL kit will be tested for prediction of contrast induced acute kidney injury" [5]. The latter is also consistent with the trial report by Shafaei-Bajestani et al., as that reported "were randomly assigned to determine the occurrence of CIAKI by measuring the plasma level of NGAL" [1, p 78]. Thus, the registration number of the trial in the trial report was also incorrect.

References

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